

Editorial for inaugural issue of “Journal of Building Materials and Structures”

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Welcome to the inauguration issue of our new publication: **Journal of Building Materials and Structures (JBMS)**. **JBMS** has been installed thanks to the open source solutions developed by [Public Knowledge Project](#). My great thanks also goes out to my co-editors and editorial office team for accepting to guide with me this journal from initial planning to the first steps it is taking now.

The main objective of **JBMS** is to provide a repository of knowledge for building materials and structural engineering sciences. The choice of open access format to **JBMS** is to ensure free access to knowledge which is linked to the economic development and seems in agreement to the spirit of scientific thought. It is important to note that all contributions, upon approval by our peer review process, are for beginning, indexed in [Google Scholar](#) and archived in the [Open Archive Initiative \(OAI\)](#).

The peer review procedure will match knowledgeable reviewers with submitted manuscripts to produce high quality articles of interest and scientific merit. The procedure is confidential so that recommendations and revisions are made in the fairest way possible. The final decision on publication will be made by the editor in charge.

As new teaching systems, such as License-Master-Doctorate (LMD) system or the national project works carried out by researchers, take root in universities and laboratories, especially across Algeria, the roles that conducting research projects and writing scientific articles play within these institutions are increasing.

In light of this development, our new journal looks at the potential of new researches and high quality contribution works within laboratories and universities, as well as the ways in which research development can impact beyond higher journal articles quality.

Finally, I thank our contributors and readers for their interest and efforts in completing this inauguration issue and I also look forward to a most interesting future for **JBMS**.